

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

YOUNG GRAMMARIANS TREND IN GERMAN LINGUISTICS AND FACTORS DETERMINING THE FORMATION OF THE YOUNG GRAMMARIANS TREND

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Abstract

The terminology “young grammarians” refers to a group of young linguists who formed in and around Leipzig in the mid-1970s. The personal classification of this group is not entirely clear - a distinction is usually made between a central group of young grammarians and scientists who have only adopted the approaches and methods of young grammarians without having been directly involved in their training. The Germanists Hermann Paul, Wilhelm Braune and Eduard Sievers, the Indo-Europeanists Hermann Osthoff and Karl Brugmann and Berthold Delbrück are usually counted among the former [1-2]. In many works, August Leskien is still counted among the central group of young grammarians, although he plays a special role in that he was the teacher of many young grammarians and had a decisive influence on the development of their research methods:

This young group of researchers saw themselves as a “new movement” in historical linguistics and rejected the term “young grammarians” for their own research direction, which has nevertheless been used in research to this day and is therefore also used in this work should.

Overall, it is difficult to describe the theories, concepts and methods of young grammar research in detail, as it was a quite heterogeneous group with different focuses and views and, above all, a group that developed immense productivity in its research area and was broad topics covered. A detailed breakdown of the individual, countless works would far exceed the scope of this work, which is therefore omitted and rather the underlying principles and commonalities that led to the success of the young grammarians and that are responsible for the current validity of the approach are highlighted, knowing full well, that it must be an idealized and reduced representation. In this presentation, similar to later structuralists and generativists, only theories that relate to the area of language change are discussed; other areas of research, such as the establishment of a general theory of language with statements about composition, deixis and anaphora, are not taken into account [3-4].

Keywords: Young grammarians, german linguistics, grammarians trend, factor, determining.

Starting from the 70s and 80s of the 19th century, a group of young linguists, first of all, took criticism of A. Schleicher as a basis for their scientific activities. They were professors at the University of Leipzig and founded a new school in linguistics - the Leipzig School of Linguistics. Friedrich Sarnke, one of the prominent representatives of the old generation of linguistics, mockingly called them "Junggrammatiker" ("Young grammarians"). Karl Brugmann, one of the talented numismatists of the Leipzig school, chose the name for the new linguistic school where they coined the word, and thus the Leipzig linguistic school became known as the linguistic school of young grammarians. It should be noted that the influence of young grammarians on the scientific thought of linguistics of their time cannot be compared with any school of linguistics [5-6]. It was, in fact, a whole linguistic trend, which spread to almost all countries; Linguistic meetings of young grammarians form the backbone of linguistic scientific fields in many countries. A. Leskien, B. Delbryuk, G. Paul, G. Osthof and K. Brugman are prominent representatives of young grammarians. All of these scholars are German linguists. However, as mentioned above, young grammarianism was a very widespread linguistic movement, and its followers were found all over the world (for example, M. Breal (1832-1915) in France; V. Thomsen (1842-1927) in Denmark, K. Werner (1846-1896) ; there were representatives, supporters

and followers of F.F.Fortunatov, F.M.Buslayev in Russia, G.I.Ascoli (1824-1907) in Italy, N.Van Wyck (1880-1941) in Holland, etc. American linguist W.D.Whitney, one of the representatives of the school of philosophical linguistics is also considered one of the young grammarians. Among the German linguists I. Schmidt (1843-1901), A. Bessenberger (1851-1922), G. Hirt (1865-1936), etc., we can mention the names of German linguists in the development of the ideas of young grammar. August Leskien 1840- Born in Kiel in 1916, died in Leipzig in 1916. He was an academician of the Berlin and Munich Academies of Sciences, and a corresponding member of the Petersburg EA since 1876. He was educated at the universities of Kiel, Leipzig, Jena and Hettigen. Mainly Indo-European linguistics, as well as conducted research on Baltic and Slavic languages. Bertold Delbrück was born in Putbus in 1842 and died in Jena in 1922. He studied in Berlin and Halle. He was mainly a specialist in the fields of Sanskrit and comparative linguistics. He differs from other young grammarians because he is more concerned with the syntax department of grammar [7-8]. The five-volume "Syntactic studies" (1871-1888) written together with F. Windisch and the two-volume work "Fundamentals of comparative grammar of Indo-European languages" written with K. Brugman are famous (the syntax section of the book was written by B. Delbryuk). A well-known theorist of young grammar is German Paul of Magdeburg. He was born in 1846 and died in Munich

in 1921. He is the author of several popular works, such as "Dictionary of the German Language" and the five-volume "Grammar of the German Language". He also wrote "Principles of Language History" (1880), which is the main expression of the theoretical views of young grammarians. This work was published in Russian in 1960. German Osthof (1847-1909) and Karl Brugmann (1849-1919) wrote the introductory part of the book "Morphological Studies" (a manifesto of the principles of young grammar and tics). There are works by K. Brugman "Grammar of the Greek language" (1885), about its modern state" etc. "Linguistics The linguistic views of young grammarians are mainly based on G. Paul's "Language historical principles", G. Osthof and K. Brugman's "Morphological studies ", expressed in the works of K. Brugman "On the modern state of linguistics" and B. Delbrück "The main issues of language research". According to young grammarians, language is a psychophysical or psychophysiological activity. This idea, which turned against the thesis of A. Schleicher, who considers language as a living organism, drew the main attention of linguists to the national language and the study of dialects [9-10]. Considering language as a physiological phenomenon at the same time opened wide horizons for the field of physiological phonetics of linguistics. On behalf of young grammarians, G. Osthof and K. Brugman explained the linguistics before them in the introduction of "Morphological studies" as follows: "No one can deny that previous linguistics focused on the object of its research - the Indo-European languages, how the human language lived and developed in general. they approached without creating any idea about what factors exist in speech activity and how these factors together affect the further development and change of language material. They studied the language with a special enthusiasm, and the speaking person very little" [19, 147]. They write: The important methodological principles of the "Young Grammar" direction are the following two provisions:

First, since it operates mechanically, each sound change occurs according to laws that cannot be excluded...

Secondly, since it is clear that the association of forms, that is, the creation of new language forms by analogy, plays a very important role in the life of new languages, the importance of this method for the enrichment of the language in ancient and most ancient times should be admitted without hesitation; and it is necessary not only to acknowledge in general, but at the same time to use this principle of explanation in the same way as it is used in the explanation of linguistic phenomena in later periods" [20, 154]. Young grammarians, sticking to these principles, which they took as a basis for their scientific activities, in Indo-European languages discovered a number of strong phonetic laws that existed. They explained the phonetic development of languages with four principles: strong sound laws that cannot be excluded, the principles of analogy, loanwords, and subsequent derivatives (neologisms). These principles are still used today as the working method of comparative-historical linguistics. has not lost its importance. Individuality and psychologism occupied the main place in the theoretical linguistic meetings of the

young grammarians. The speaking individual was the main research object for the young grammarians. This is also specially noted by G. Paul [11-12]:

"Language really exists only in the individual" [10, 104], "Only the language of the individual has real reality" [10, 104].

Young grammarians gave great preference to historicity. They did not consider linguistics, which was not based on history, to be a science. G. Paul wrote:

"All linguistics is history".

In the introduction of "Morphological studies", which is considered a manifesto of young grammarians, their views on language are reflected. This work was published in 1878 by K. Brugman and H. Osthof. Young grammarians opposed A. Schleicher's naturalism and did not accept Steintal's psychology of peoples. "Language exists only in the individual, and the individual is the cause of changes in the language," young grammarians preferred to study living languages and dialects. And they were of the opinion that their predecessors were interested in learning written languages and were busy restoring the Indo-European language. And they hardly learned the living human language, folk dialects. However, living languages can provide more material for determining the patterns of language development. The studies of the young grammarians, who thoroughly study the language, about the sound system and history of the language, are especially distinguished. According to them, each sound change is subject to a certain principle. Likewise, analogy is the most important factor in the formation of new language forms. The main goal of the young grammarians in studying the living human language and folk dialects was to study the history of the language. In this regard, Vilem Matezius, the founder of the Prague Linguistic Association, wrote in his article "Where have we come in Linguistics" that historical research is considered the only scientific method in linguistic works: even when living dialects are studied, its results are mainly used to solve historical problems. And F. de Saussure formulates the most important services of young grammarians in the development of the science of language in the following way: their service consisted in putting the results of comparison into a historical perspective and thereby arranging the facts in their natural order.

The first school of linguistics that criticized the "young grammarians" for their "pettiness" and severed all ties with their tradition was the "Words and Things" school. The scientific principles of the school are reflected in the articles "Things and Words", "On Phonetic Laws (against young grammarians)", "Notes on Language, Thinking and General Linguistics" dedicated to problematic issues by its head, Hugo Schuchardt. H. Schuchardt did not accept theses of young grammarians about the inviolability of phonetic laws. He said that I consider the doctrine of the inviolability of phonetic laws to be a brake on the further development of science in connection with the law of causality.

The "things and words" school mostly studied the semantics of words. According to them, in order to understand the essence of words, it is necessary to study the history of the concepts they call. Because words do not pass from one language to another alone, but with

the things they denote. According to the author of "Things and Words", the study of things and words should be done simultaneously. And the author of the article considered the explanation of the relationship between words and things as the most important part of the methodology of this field of research. H. Shukhardt spoke about the role of mixing in the development of the language in his article "On the issue of mixing of languages" against the young grammarians who started from the principle of the kinship of languages. One of the critics of A. Schleicher's "genealogy of languages" theory, a prominent proponent of comparative-historical linguistics, was A. Schleicher's student H. Schuhardt. According to the linguist who replaced the principle of genealogical classification with the theory of geographical continuity of languages, the mixing or crossing of languages plays an important role in the formation of all language groups.

"Critic of the old, harbinger of the new", H. Shukhardt also said that the idea of dependence between the language and the geographical location of the people carrying it was instilled in his students by their teacher A. Schleicher.

One of the schools of linguistics that arose during the struggle with young grammarians is the school of aesthetic linguistics, which was headed by the German scientist Karl Fossler. The scientific principles of this school are reflected in the scientist's works "Positivism and Idealism in Linguistics", "Language as Creativity and Development", "Culture and Language of France". K. Fossler, who replaced G. Paul's thesis "every linguistics is history" with the proposition "every linguistics is an aesthetic linguistics", approached language from an aesthetic point of view, as well as prioritized the expressive function of language over other functions.

According to K. Fossler, who put forward the thesis that "according to its essence, every language expression is an individual spiritual creativity", every person creates his own language. And that is why K. Fossler did not consider phonetics, morphology and syntax to be a science and gave the main priority to stylistics. He said that this whole set of grammatical subjects (phonetics, morphology and syntax) is an endless graveyard made by tireless positivists (young grammarians—Q.C). Who has not been out of breath here?! The bridge from syntax to stylistics means bringing the dead back to life. K. Fossler considered the generality of language intelligence as the basis for communication between people. According to him, if people can communicate with each other through language, this is not due to the commonality of language material, structure, or language laws, but due to the commonality of linguistic intelligence. "Language is an expression of the soul," said K. Fossler, who saw the reason for the development of language in the human soul and explained that development with aesthetic reasons. He said that phonetics, acoustics, physiology of the speech organs, anthropology, and what else—merely descriptive studies in general linguistics—are subsidiary subjects; they can only show us the conditions under which language developed, but not the reason for this development. And then he added that the reason is the human spirit

with its tireless individual intuition. As is known, the young grammarians saw the task of the linguist in collecting language material. The goal of aesthetic idealism led by K. Fossler was to determine the causal relationship between language phenomena [12-13].

Conclusions

Finally, they liked to study language facts in isolation rather than within a system. According to young grammarians, only in this case can the facts of the language be studied comprehensively and deeply. These last two principles are known in the history of linguistics as the historicism and atomism of young grammarians.

Young grammarians have a number of shortcomings, two of which should be mentioned in particular:

1. The important shortcoming of young grammarians was their atomism and historicism. Their atomism and historicism did not allow for the study of language as a system, and thus the study of language was limited to tracing the history of individual isolated linguistic facts. At the same time, this makes the sound structure of the language the object of study of physiological phonetics only, and thus the regularities of the language system were compromised to sound laws without exception.

2. The science of linguistics was limited only to phonetics and grammar. Other areas of linguistics, such as lexicology, stylistics, etc. was not involved in the study. At the end of the 19th century, the linguistic schools criticized young grammarians and this was the main fault.

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